

Further addition to the Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) fauna of Iran

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Abstract: In this faunistic paper, 24 species of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) in 22 genera and 13 subfamilies were collected and determined from different regions of Iran, which among them, seven species are new country records: *Allomacrus arcticus* (Holmgren, 1880) (Cyllocerinae), *Ctenochira xanthopyga* (Holmgren, 1857) (Tryphoninae), *Euceros kiushuensis* Uchida, 1958 (Eucerotinae), *Mesostenus funebris* Gravenhorst, 1829, *Trychosis gradaria* (Tschek, 1871) (Cryptinae), *Metopius (Ceratopius) mediterraneus* Clément, 1930 (Metopiinae), and *Rhimphoctona (Xylophylax) lucida* (Clément, 1924) (Campopleginae).

Introduction

The Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea), known as Darwin wasps, is a comparatively large clade of cosmopolitan parasitoid wasps (Quicke 2015; Klopffstein *et al.* 2019). This family comprises over than 25,000 valid species distributed along 42 subfamilies (Yu *et al.* 2016; Bennett *et al.* 2019). Ichneumonid wasps are solitary parasitoids that mainly attack larvae and pupae of Lepidoptera, Coleoptera and Hymenoptera, many of them constitute important agricultural pests (Gauld 1991; Quicke 2015;

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Belokobylskij and Lelej 2019).

The family Ichneumonidae of Iran has not been studied enough, although it is one of the most interesting places in the Palaearctic Region, due to having an extremely varying topography and various kinds of climates. In the first catalogue of the Iranian Ichneumonidae (Kolarov & Ghahari, 2005), 144 species were listed, and the updated catalogue from Yu et al. (2016) comprises only 622 species. The goal of this research is to study the fauna of Iranian Ichneumonidae and introducing seven new country records.

Material and methods

The specimens of this faunistic investigation were collected by sweeping net and Malaise traps from different areas of Iran. The collected materials were sorted to subfamily based on Broad (2015) and Broad et al. (2018), and genus level by Townes (1969, 1970a, b, 1971). The determined specimens were confirmed by the first author and some other authorized taxonomists. Most of the materials are preserved in the insect collection of Qaemshahr Islamic Azad University, and some others in private collection of the first author. Here we follow Yu et al. (2016) for nomenclature, classification, and distributional and host data.

Results

In total, 24 species of Ichneumonidae under 12 subfamilies, Adelognathinae, Banchinae, Campopleginae, Cremastinae, Cryptinae, Ctenopelmatinae, Cylloceriinae, Eucerotinae, Ichneumoninae, Mesochorinae, Metopiinae, Orthocentrinae and Tryphoninae were collected and determined from different regions of Iran.

Subfamily Adelognathinae Thomson, 1888

Genus *Adelognathus* Holmgren, 1857

***Adelognathus brevicornis* Holmgren, 1857**

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 3♀♀, August 2014. Mazandaran province, Sari, Semeskandeh, 1♀, September 2019.

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General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Canada, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Ireland, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom, United States of America.

Host records: Unknown.

Subfamily Banchinae Wesmael, 1845

***Glypta sculpturata* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Guilan province, Lahijan, 1♂, June 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Ematurga atomaria* (Linnaeus) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae).

Subfamily Campopleginae Förster, 1869

Genus *Olesicampe* Förster, 1869

***Olesicampe longipes* (Müller, 1776)**

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Bonab, Chopoghloo, 1♂, September 2016.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, United Kingdom.

Host records: Unknown.

Genus *Rhimphoctona* Förster, 1869

***Rhimphoctona (Xylophylax) lucida* (Clément, 1924)**

Material examined: Ardebil province, Bilehsavar, 2♂♂, 3.vii.2017.
New record for the fauna of Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, China, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Montenegro, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Switzerland.

Host records: *Monochamus saltuarius* Gebler, *Tetropium duscum* (Fabricius), and *Tetropium gabrieli* Weise (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae).

Subfamily Cremastinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Cremastus* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Cremastus dalmatinus* Strobl, 1904**

Material examined: Chaharmahal-Bakhtiari province, Lordegan, 2♀♀, August 2015.

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General distribution: Romania, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkey, former Yugoslavia.

Host records: Unknown.

Subfamily Cryptinae Kirby, 1837

Genus *Hoplocryptus* Thomson, 1873

***Hoplocryptus magrettii* (Kriechbaumer, 1893)**

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Marand, Darandash, 2♂♂, September 2016.

General distribution: Austria, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey.

Host records: *Osmia inermis* (Zetterstedt) (Hymenoptera: Apidae).

Genus *Mesostenus* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Mesostenus funebris* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Behshahr, 2♀♀, July 2017. *New record for the fauna of Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain.

Host records: *Zygaena lonicerae* (Scheven) (Lepidoptera: Zygaenidae).

Genus *Oresbius* Marshall, 1867

***Oresbius galactinus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Lorestan province, Aligoodarz, 2♀♀, June 2018.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Korea, Lithuania, Pakistan, Poland, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Deilephila elpenor* (Linnaeus) (Lepidoptera: Sphingidae), and *Synanthedon tipuliformis* (Clerck) (Lepidoptera: Sesiidae).

Genus *Polytribax* Förster, 1869

***Polytribax rufipes* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Zanjan province, Khorram-Darreh, 2♂♂, July 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom.

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Host records: *Bupalus piniarius* (Linnseus), *Macaria liturata* (Clerck) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae), and *Zysandra coridon* (Poda) (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae).

Genus *Trychosis* Förster, 1869

***Trychosis gradaria* (Tschek, 1871)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Mako, 1♀, September 2018. *New record for the fauna of Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

Host records: Unknown.

Subfamily Ctenopelmatinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Barytarbes* Förster, 1869

***Barytarbes flavicornis* (Thomson, 1892)**

Material examined: Khorasan-e Razavi province, Ferdos, 3♀♀, August 2013. Semnan province, Shahrood, Jangal-e Abr, 2♀♀, July 2018.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom.

Host records: Unknown.

Genus *Phobetres* Förster, 1869

***Phobetres chrysostomus* (Gravenhorst, 1820)**

Material examined: Hamedan province, Gol-Tappeh, 2♀♀, 1♂, September 2015.

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom.

Host records: Unknown.

Genus *Trematopygus* Holmgren, 1857

***Trematopygus melanocerus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Langrood, Liseh-Rood, 1♀, May 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

Host records: Unknown.

Subfamily Cyllocerinae Wahl, 1990

Genus *Allomacrus* Förster, 1869

***Allomacrus arcticus* (Holmgren, 1880)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Shahreza, 1♂, May 2013; Chaharmahal-Bakhtiari province, Lordegan, 2♂♂, 1♀, August 2015.

New record for the fauna of Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Canada, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United States of America.

Host records: Unknown.

Subfamily Eucerotinae Viereck, 1919

Genus *Euceros* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Euceros kiushuensis* Uchida, 1958**

Material examined: Alborz province, Nazar-Abad, 1♀, June 2013.

New record for the fauna of Iran.

General distribution: China, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Poland, Romania, Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Host records: *Phobocampe unicincta* (Gravenhorst) (Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae).

Subfamily Ichneumoninae Latreille, 1802

Genus *Dicaelotus* Wesmael, 1845

***Dicaelotus parvulus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Absh-Ahmad, 2♂♂, 21.v.2016, det. A.M. Tereshkin.

General distribution: Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Turkmenistan, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Exoteleia dodecella* (Linnaeus) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) and *Lobesia botrana* (Denis and Schiffermüller) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae).

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Genus *Epitomus* Förster, 1869

***Epitomus infuscatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Bijar, 1♀, June 2016, det. A.M. Tereshkin.

General distribution: Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Elachista humilis* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Elachistidae).

Subfamily Mesochorinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Cidaphus* Förster, 1869

***Cidaphus atricilla* (Haliday, 1838)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Salmas, 1♀, August 2015.

General distribution: Austria, China, Finland, Germany, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Enicospilus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae).

Subfamily Metopiinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Metopius* Panzer, 1806

***Metopius (Ceratopius) mediterraneus* Clément, 1930**

Material examined: Ardebil province, Bilehsavar, 2♀♀, 3.vii.2017.
New record for the fauna of Iran.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Italy, Kazakhstan, Norway, Poland, Russia, Ukraine.

Host records: Unknown.

Genus *Trieces* Townes, 1946

***Trieces rufimitranae* Aeschlimann, 1973**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Naqadeh, 1♀, July 2015.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, France, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Host records: *Zeiraphera rufimitrana* (Herrich-Schäffer) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae).

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Subfamily Neorhacodinae Hedicke, 1922

Genus *Neorhacodes* Hedicke, 1922

***Neorhacodes enslini* (Ruschka, 1922)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Tonekabon, Jangal-e 2000, 2♀♀, June 2015. *New record for the fauna of Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Spilomena differens* Blüthgen, *Spilomena enslini* Blüthgen, and *Spilomena troglodytes* Vander Linden (Hymenoptera: Crabronidae).

Subfamily Orthocentrinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Aperileptus* Förster, 1869

***Aperileptus impurus* Förster, 1871**

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Qorveh, 1♂, 1♀, September 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Sweden, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Anomalomyia guttata* (Hutton) (Diptera: Mycetophilidae).

Subfamily Tryphoninae Shuckard, 1840

Genus *Ctenochira* Förster, 1869

***Ctenochira xanthopyga* (Holmgren, 1857)**

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Absh-Ahmad, 2♀♀, 21.v.2016. *New record for the fauna of Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom.

Host records: Unknown.

Genus *Phytodietus* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Phytodietus astutus* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Miandoab, Hesarlu, 1♂, 1♀, April 2013.

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General distribution: Bulgaria, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Sweden, United Kingdom.

Host records: *Agonopterix heracliana* (Linnaeus) (Lepidoptera: Depressariidae).

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